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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Requisitos de calidad y capacidad de los vietnamitas de hoy ante el impacto de la cuarta revolución industrial /DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8319553

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Resumen

La Revolución Industrial 4.0 ha tenido un profundo impacto en todos los ámbitos de la vida socioeconómica de Vietnam, incluida la cuestión del desarrollo humano. Para aprovechar las oportunidades y minimizar los impactos negativos, Vietnam necesita evaluar exhaustivamente el impacto de esta revolución, incluido el impacto en la construcción del pueblo vietnamita. El artículo se realiza con el objetivo de aclarar cuestiones relacionadas con los requisitos de calidad y la capacidad del pueblo vietnamita actual bajo el impacto de la revolución industrial 4.0. Los resultados muestran que, bajo el impacto de la revolución industrial 4.0, los requisitos sobre calidad y capacidad del pueblo vietnamita se centran ahora en una serie de aspectos como: Personas calificadas y capacitadas La mano de obra de alto nivel cumple y se adapta en gran medida a los requisitos de la revolución industrial 4.0, mientras que el nivel laboral, los malos hábitos, la disciplina laboral y la capacidad de trabajo en equipo de muchos vietnamitas siguen siendo de bajo nivel; la capacidad práctica, la capacidad en lenguas extranjeras y la adaptabilidad al competitivo entorno industrial; los requisitos sobre el perfeccionamiento de los valores humanos vietnamitas con la fractura del sistema de valores y las normas culturales entre generaciones debido al reverso de la revolución industrial 4.0; los vietnamitas necesitan una nueva moral y actualización de las capacidades. El artículo ha esbozado cuatro soluciones para promover los requisitos de calidad y la capacidad de los vietnamitas de hoy bajo el impacto de la revolución industrial 4.0. La limitación de este estudio es que no ha identificado y analizado los factores que afectan a la construcción humana y el desarrollo para cumplir con los requisitos de las políticas de industrialización y modernización del país a 2030 con una visión a 2045 en Vietnam.

Palabras clave: Pueblo, pueblo de Vietnam, revolución industrial 4.0, Vietnam

Abstract

The quality and capacity of today Vietnamese people required by the fourth industrial revolution

The Industrial Revolution 4.0 has had a profound impact on all areas of socio-economic life in Vietnam, including the issue of human development. In order to take advantage of opportunities and minimize negative impacts, Vietnam needs to assess the impact of this revolution comprehensively, including the impact on building Vietnamese people. The article is made with the aim of clarifying issues related to the quality and capacity requirements of Vietnamese people today under the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0. The results show that, under the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0, the

requirements on quality and capacity of Vietnamese people are now focused on a number of aspects such as: Qualified and skilled people High labor force meets and adapts highly to the requirements of the industrial revolution 4.0 while the labor level, bad habits, labor discipline and teamwork ability of many Vietnamese people are still at the highest level. low level; practical ability, foreign language ability and adaptability to the competitive industrial environment; requirements on the perfection of Vietnamese human values with the fracture of the value system and cultural standards between generations due to the reverse side of the industrial revolution 4.0; Vietnamese people need a new morality and Update skills. The article has outlined four solutions to promote the requirements of quality and capacity of Vietnamese people today under the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0. The limitation of this study is that it has not identified and analyzed factors affecting human construction and development to meet the requirements of policies on industrialization and modernization of the country to 2030 with a vision to 2045 in Vietnam.

Keywords: People, people of Vietnam, industrial revolution 4.0, Vietnam.

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1.- Introduction

The Industrial Revolution 4.0 is based on digital technology to build a hyper-connected world and integrate smart technologies to optimize production processes and methods. Industry 4.0 is based on the development of information technology, digital, internet, global connectivity in many fields and every person. The process of globalization and international economic integration leading to globalization and international integration of people, requires basic and urgent qualities and capacities to adapt to the changes of society. The industrial revolution 4.0 brings great opportunities for developing countries in general, including Vietnam, which can shorten the development process by "taking shortcuts, taking the lead", developing leaps and bounds to high technology. than. This is an opportunity to improve labor productivity, competitiveness of traditional industries and occupations as well as access to world markets on digital and Internet platforms for fast and sustainable economic growth with high value. increase in the global supply chain. Industry 4.0 brings opportunities for sustainable development of the digital economy [18, 48], digital society, digital culture, smart production and services; economic, industrial, agricultural, cultural, tourism, service, financial, banking, logistic, robotics... intelligentization. Industry 4.0 also helps increase labor productivity, save production and management costs, bringing great benefits to the State, businesses and people. Industry 4.0 has a strong impact on the field of culture and people. Connecting to the Internet of Things, big data, artificial intelligence, cloud computing ... helps people access the vast amount of information of all humanity. Social media (Facebook, Twitter, you tube, Instagram, TikTok...) have become a new cultural phenomenon; become the place where diverse and rich

information and cultural activities take place, containing many values and even counter-values, spreading cultural soft power and limiting, undermining the national cultural soft power... It is necessary to recognize the downside of technology, changes in the way of communication, information and culture on the Internet also put people and social culture in many unpredictable "dangers", "uncertainties". We will face many challenges, especially in the fields of cyber security, cultural security, human security, non-traditional security, high-tech crime, transnational crime... social media, telecommunications networks, and the internet facilitate exchanges and absorption of the cultural quintessence of mankind, and at the same time, there is a fierce struggle to preserve the national cultural identity. protection of political institutions, national security, cultural security and human security. In that context, the perception of the requirements of the quality and capacity of the Vietnamese people today before the impact of the fourth industrial revolution is a matter of practical significance and urgent for the present now in Vietnam.

Research question

Question 1: What are the requirements on the quality and capacity of Vietnamese people today under the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0?

Question 2: What are the basic solutions to promote the quality and capacity of Vietnamese people today before the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0?

Research purposes

The purpose of the article is to analyze and clarify issues related to the quality and capacity of Vietnamese people today before the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0.

Research Methods

- Group of theoretical research methods: using methods of analysis, synthesis, and systematization of theories to identify instrumental concepts and build a theoretical framework for the article.
- Group of practical research methods:
 - Observation method: Observing the impacts of the industrial revolution 4.0 on Vietnamese people today.
 - In-depth interview method: Collect opinions of employees, managers, enterprises, and researchers to find out about the requirements for quality and capacity of Vietnamese people before the impact and influence of industrial revolution 4.0. In addition, the article also uses a synthesis of specific research methods such as: deductive and inductive, logic and history, comparison and contrast between theory and practice.

2.- Results

Requirements on the quality and capacity of Vietnamese people today before the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0

It can be generalized that the main features of the 4.0 industrial revolution are: (i) based on the combination of new sensor technology, big data analysis, cloud computing and the internet of things. promote the development of automated machinery and intelligent production systems. (ii), using 3D printing technology to produce complete products by unifying production lines without having to assemble auxiliary equipment - this technology also allows people to can print new products using non-traditional methods, bypassing the middlemen and reducing production costs as much as possible. (iii), nanotechnology and new materials create new material structures with wide applications in almost all fields. (iv), artificial intelligence and cybernetics allow humans to control remotely, without limitations in space and time, to interact faster and more accurately. The essence of the industrial revolution 4.0 is based on the foundation of digital technology and the integration of intelligent technologies in the fields of physics and biology with the center being the development of artificial intelligence (AI). connected objects (IoT), big data (Big Data), nanotechnology. The fields of this revolution set requirements for Vietnamese people in a number of areas as follows:

Firstly, people with high qualifications and labor skills meet and adapt to the requirements of the industrial revolution 4.0 while the labor level, bad habits, labor discipline and ability to work the group of many Vietnamese people is still at a low level

With the strong development of technology in the industrial revolution 4.0, it will change the nature of work significantly for all industries and professions. Requirements on labor qualifications and skills are put first to adapt to modern machinery and technical means, accompanied by an increasing degree of specialization, requiring the ability to work. independence and ability to work in a team, sense of labor discipline. While we go up to build socialism from a backward agricultural country, Vietnamese people, besides virtues and good qualities, still have many bad habits such as opportunism, factions; greedy for fame; lack of sense of law compliance; waste; The ability to work as a team is not high, ... These are the weaknesses, and at the same time, the challenges that make us lose the opportunities brought by the industrial revolution 4.0, leading to lagging behind other countries. other. In addition, the emergence of many new professions brought about by the industrial revolution 4.0 requires the adaptability of Vietnamese people.

The rapid development and application of modern technologies from the industrial revolution 4.0 with the focus on the formation of smart factories, digital factories - where machines and devices will be connected, automatically decide the entire operation of the factory from collecting, analyzing requirements, building production plans. Therefore, machine labor and automation will replace manual labor. On the one hand, it requires

human quality, but on the other hand, it also changes human labor methods, making many industries tradition will be lost, many new fields of labor will appear, the time of appearance and disappearance may be very short. This requires people to have enough qualities and abilities to adapt. Meanwhile, many Vietnamese people who have low labor skills but are affected by conservative and stagnant ideology will find it difficult to adapt to the rapid change of new working methods.

Second, practical ability, foreign language ability and adaptability to the industrial competitive environment of Vietnamese people

The industrial revolution 4.0 makes the world more and more "flat", which means that countries and peoples are closer together, the degree of connection is closer, therefore, it requires individuals to understand foreign countries. language to exchange and link at work. In addition, the practical and most direct requirement for workers, in the industrial revolution 4.0, the development competition between countries is becoming more and more fierce, due to economic factors. regulations. While our foreign language ability is still quite low, the current training is not suitable in both quantity and quality.

College and university training still accounts for a large proportion, which is the cause of the surplus of teachers and the shortage of workers. Teaching methods are still outdated, and new modern technologies have not been applied. In the work of curriculum development, there is a lack of practical programs, leading to a lack of opportunities for learners to apply the knowledge learned in school to specific problems of society. With the psychology of degrees, most learners choose to study at university or graduate school without paying attention to human resource needs [20, 815] as well as vocational training, which leads to the current shortage of teachers and workers. Today and the situation of workers who have university degrees but accept to do jobs that do not need technical expertise, ...

Third, the requirement for the perfection of Vietnamese human values with the fracture of the value system and cultural standards between generations created by the reverse side of the industrial revolution 4.0

In the era of information technology boom, the rapid development of the internet and social networks; electronic media; entertainment television channels; ... bring useful information, create conditions for people to access information conveniently and easily; ability to share, high connection, ... Besides, it also leaves many consequences such as: addiction to online games; the increase in slang language, sign language distorts and loses the purity of Vietnamese, making each individual a closed space lacking cohesion and sharing among members, lack of attention to social issues and reduce the responsibility of individuals to the community. The rifts in behavior and lifestyle between generations in the same family are complicated, many conflicts are difficult to reconcile.

Domestic violence between husband and wife, parents and children; competition for land assets, etc., creating barriers and hidden conflicts between generations in the context of transformation, searching and establishing suitable family models. In the current context of globalization and deep international integration, a fully developed Vietnamese person must be a cultured person, bearing the Vietnamese national cultural identity and the ability to absorb cultural quintessence. of humanity, reflected in the quality of global citizenship. The Vietnamese people's comprehensive development of virtue, intelligence, body and beauty must include: Having a passionate patriotism from love of the homeland, love of people, and love of good traditional values of the nation. expressed through loving and valuing people not only within family, school, national but also international. It is also a person with a life ideal, a sense of responsibility, a will to strive constantly, a simple lifestyle for the community, and act with diligence, thrift, integrity, righteousness, justice, and impartiality. It is necessary to build an education for people who have enough physical and mental health to promote their intellect, maximize their creative work potential, and have the ability to self-study for life.

Fourth, Vietnamese people need a new morality

Talking about ethics refers to the system of rules and standards of ethical relations, corresponding to the period of accelerating industrialization, modernization, industrial revolution 4.0, building a market economy, and socializing. international integration to distinguish it from the system of rules and ethical standards that existed in previous periods. The new morality of Vietnamese people today is not separate from the good traditional moral content of the nation, but it is the acquisition and inheritance of the good content of the nation's traditional morality., and at the same time, modifying some old content to suit modern society, discarding outdated content that is no longer relevant to the current social context.

The new morality contains in it a wide range of contents from the ideal of striving for national independence, a prosperous country, a rich people, a strong country, a democratic, equitable, and civilized society to thrifty behavior, civilized lifestyle, honesty, humanity, healthy lifestyle. The moral content, or in other words, the ethical aspect in each person never stands alone, separate from other aspects, but often mixes together, intertwines, and complements each other. each other to create the quality of the human model of the time, of each historical period, both inheriting and absorbing the features in the human model of the past and bringing new features specific to the human model. of the new period. Even the old features acquired from the past, its content, spirit and character have also been marked by the new era, or modified to suit new conditions. A simple, simple, sincere, modest lifestyle, thrift, reasonable and reasonable behavior is also a content of the new morality.

Vietnamese people have a thrifty, simple, sincere, simple and humble lifestyle as a natural and inevitable feature, derived from their living and working conditions. In the context of international integration, a pragmatic, money-based, lavish and wasteful

lifestyle has been more or less affecting a part of the population. Therefore, it is even more necessary to promote the standards of thrift, simple, sincere, simple and modest lifestyle as a requirement for modern Vietnamese people. That will help the building of Vietnamese people in the current period have the right orientation, prevent and prevent the harmful effects of a lifestyle contrary to fine customs and traditions, alien to the human nature of the people Vietnam.

Fifth, update skills

In addition, in the context of globalization and international integration, the rapid development of the industrial revolution 4.0 has profoundly changed the way of living and working in interactions with each other. The constant change of social circumstances requires each person to constantly update their skills and perfect themselves to adapt to the new situation. The requirements of modernization, internationalization and the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0 have set the responsibility of each person to be proactive with themselves and with society, towards global citizens. A global citizen is a person who has the ability to act cooperatively, responsibly and creatively to solve common problems of the community, contributing to making the locality, the country, the world better and sustainable development; communicate and adapt in different cultural environments, multicultural environments; respect for human rights and diversity; respect and promote the cultural values of their nation and country, and at the same time consciously learn the cultural quintessence of other peoples and countries.

The views on comprehensive citizenship education towards global citizens have now been reflected in the determination of the goal of renovating programs, textbooks, and general education "to develop Vietnamese people comprehensively in German, intellectual, physical, aesthetic, towards "global citizens" (Decision 404/QĐ-TTg, dated March 27, 2015, of the Prime Minister of Vietnam, "On approval of program renewal scheme , textbooks, general education") and concretize them into the main qualities of patriotism, compassion, hard work, honesty, responsibility and comprehensive development of capabilities including common competencies, such as autonomy and self-study, communication and cooperation, problem-solving and creativity; specific competencies, such as language, computing, science, and technology, information technology, aesthetic ability, physical ability.

Basic solutions to promote the quality and capacity of Vietnamese people today under the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0

Firstly, it is necessary to have a strategy to develop Vietnamese people in the era of industrial revolution 4.0.

The Communist Party of Vietnam is well aware of this problem and affirmed: "Soon there will be a national strategy on building a Vietnamese family, contributing to preserving and developing the traditional values of Vietnamese culture and people.

South, nurture and educate the young generation. Unite and build a common value system of Vietnamese people in the period of accelerating industrialization, modernization and international integration" [6, 223]. All undertakings and policies in the Party's human development strategy must always be people-oriented, all for the sake of people, and must consider "People are the center of the development strategy and at the same time the subject of development". [6, 76-77] in the development of society. These guidelines and policies must be specific and clear in determining purposes, standards and principles for organizations and individuals to follow.

Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to renew the thinking and state management method for building people in the era of industrial revolution 4.0. At the same time, build a mechanism for coordination and responsibility sharing among political, economic and cultural fields to improve the quality and effectiveness of human construction. The State should prioritize the transfer and strong application of new technologies in industries and fields; responsible for promoting scientific and technological research, creating a favorable and supportive environment with focus and focus so that people and businesses are decisive actors to participate in the industrial revolution 4.0.

In addition, it is necessary to build a cultural value system and a standard value system of Vietnamese people in the new era in order to have a basis for human development. The cultural value system and the standard value system of Vietnamese people must be both suitable to the traditional cultural values of the nation and to the cultural values of the times in order to build the people. Vietnamese people with full qualities and capabilities, must be national, modern and humane; both capable of taking on new responsibilities in the process of industrialization, modernization, international integration and defense of the socialist Fatherland in the new situation. This standard value system is the basis for the fields of culture, health, education, ... at all levels and branches to have grounds to cultivate Vietnamese people's values, depending on the field of activity of the Vietnamese people. me. Along with that, there must be a mechanism to "repel bad, evil, lowly, backward; combat wrong, negative views, acts, etc. that corrupt people. There are solutions to overcome these problems. limitations of Vietnamese people" [7, 51].

Second, make the most of all conditions brought by the industrial revolution 4.0 to develop Vietnamese people.

The industrial revolution 4.0 opens up many opportunities and poses many challenges for each country, organization and individual; has been and is having an increasingly strong impact on all areas of the country's economic and social life. Over the past time, our Party and State have led and directed all levels and branches to promote the application and development of science, technology and innovation, research, capture, and improve access to and actively participate in the industrial revolution 4.0. The Prime Minister has issued a directive on improving the capacity to

approach the industrial revolution 4.0 and approved the Scheme to promote the sharing economic model. However, the level of active participation in the industrial revolution 4.0 in Vietnam is still low. Accordingly, actively participating in the industrial revolution 4.0 is an indispensable and objective requirement; is a task of particularly important strategic significance, both urgent and long-term, of both the political system and the whole society, closely associated with the deep international integration process; effectively take advantage of opportunities offered by the industrial revolution 4.0 to promote innovation and high-quality human resources; improve the quality of life and welfare of the people. It is necessary to focus on taking advantage of all achievements for economic development, hunger eradication and poverty alleviation, raising incomes, and raising living standards for the people, thereby creating material conditions for human development through meeting human needs well, and at the same time creating equal opportunities in accessing development resources and enjoying basic services and social benefits, reducing the gap in living standards between rural and urban areas. urban areas, among regions of the country. These are opportunities for people to improve their material living conditions as a foundation for comprehensive development. However, economic development must be associated with cultural development to create sustainable development, thus, along with economic development, culture must be developed.

Third, focus on cultural development and education and training

Culture is the spiritual foundation of society, the endogenous force that makes the society sustainable development, culture also nurtures human values, is a measure of human development level, makes human comprehensive developer. From the role of culture in human and social development, we must continue to develop deeply and improve the quality of an advanced culture imbued with national identity, building culture in the economy and society. politics, making culture permeate all areas of social life. Building and perfecting goes hand in hand with improving the quality and operational efficiency of cultural institutions. In addition, the industrial revolution 4.0 requires people who have the ability to think and create, innovate, analyze and synthesize information, have the ability to work independently and make decisions based on the basis of information. data analysis facility. If learners are equipped with broad knowledge, thinking capacity, expressive ability, ... then they will be more successful in life. The orientation of educational innovation towards "liberation" has become a modern philosophy that many leading universities in the world pursue.

Accordingly, in education, it is necessary to "strongly shift the educational process from equipping knowledge to developing learners' capabilities and qualities" [8, 115]. That is, it is necessary to promote the human factor, towards maximizing the creativity of individuals, liberating thinking, evoking the creativity inside the human brain, creating conditions for them to bring into full play. personal abilities. These are: innovating teaching and learning methods on the basis of applying digital technology; take the assessment of enterprises as a measure for the training quality of universities.

It is necessary to equip learners with the ability to apply knowledge in many different fields to solve a difficult problem. Instead of just delving into a specific field, liberal-oriented learners will explore and discover problems, ideas, and solutions in a wide range of fields, from art to literature, language, to philosophy, history, mathematics and science. Spending a lot of time teaching learners about methods, skills, self-study, teaching how to use and exploit equipment, linking theory with practice, etc ability to quickly adapt to situations, be capable of lifelong learning and have high responsibilities to family, society and the Fatherland.

3. Conclusions

The industrial revolution 4.0 has had a profound impact on all areas of social life, it has both set new requirements for human development, and at the same time created preconditions and conditions for human development. favorable for human development in Vietnam. Vietnam belongs to the group of countries that are in the transition period of the industrial revolution 4.0 with many development opportunities in the fields of production, services, agriculture, banking, and finance. The development and application of new technological achievements will bring economic growth to Vietnam, directly contributing to setting the requirements for the quality and capacity of Vietnamese people today before the work. movement of the industrial revolution 4.0. In the period under the impact and influence of the Covid-19 pandemic, although the world situation has many fluctuations and complicated developments, the domestic situation is still difficult, but the whole country's economy still shows signs of improvement. positive and positive, difficulties of enterprises are gradually removed, social security is ensured. Industry 4.0 is a combination of technology in the fields of physics, digital technology and biology, creating completely new production possibilities and having a profound impact on economic and political life., society of the world in general, including Vietnam.

This study was conducted with the aim of clarifying issues related to the quality and capacity of Vietnamese people today under the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0. The results show that, under the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0, the requirements on quality and capacity of Vietnamese people are now focused on a number of aspects such as: Qualified and skilled people High labor force meets and adapts highly to the requirements of the industrial revolution 4.0 while the labor level, bad habits, labor discipline and teamwork ability of many Vietnamese people are still at the highest level. low level; practical ability, foreign language ability and adaptability to the competitive industrial environment; requirements on the perfection of Vietnamese human values with the fracture of the value system and cultural standards between generations due to the reverse side of the industrial revolution 4.0; Vietnamese people need new morality; Update skills. The article has outlined four solutions to promote the quality and capacity of Vietnamese people today under the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0. The limitation of this rescuer is that he has not pointed out and analyzed the characteristics and factors affecting the promotion of the quality and capacity of Vietnamese people today before the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0.

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